

Mount Athos

also known as “Monastic Community of Mount Athos, Holy Mountain”

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Entry tags: Religious Complex, Macedonia, Russian Orthodox, Religious Place, Orthodox Christianity, Christian Traditions, Orthodoxy, Monasticism, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Monastery, Religious Group, Greece

The Monastic Community of Mount Athos is geographically defined by the boundaries of the Athos peninsula, the easternmost leg of the larger Chalkidiki peninsula, being a self-governing community within the Greek territory. Mount Athos is a living worshipping and hesychastic community with continuous and uninterrupted presence that spans over a millennium. It consists of twenty sovereign Monasteries, skētes (smaller communities of Christian hermits with a common area of worship), cells and kathismata (units with a small church operated by the monks living under the spiritual and administrative supervision of a monastery) scattered throughout the peninsula. For more than a thousand years successively, the Holy Mountain operates as one of the most important cultural conservatories for both the Orthodox Christian and the Greek civilization. Directly and tangibly associated with the Byzantine world in all of its religious and cultural manifestations, the twelve-century years old monastic community constitutes a living record of human activities, preserving an enormous wealth of historic, artistic and cultural elements. At the end of the 9th century, there were many hermits and small monastic communities on Athos. However, most of the monks were still hermits, living in improvised huts, eating the fruits of wild trees, and suffering the effects of frequent pirate raids. This situation changed with the arrival of St. Athanasius the Athonite. In 961, Athanasios began to build the Great Lavra, a monastery to which the Emperor Nikephoros Phokas himself retired in his old age. Athanasios's vigorous building activity provoked the opposition of most of the ascetics, who accused him before Emperor John Tsimiskes of corrupting the character of Mount Athos. The Emperor responded with an imperial chrysobull, the “Tragos”, which is the oldest document bearing an imperial signature. The “Tragos” was the first rule for Mount Athos, and lent further support to what Athanasios was doing. By the time he died in 1000, Athanasios not only had constructed the large and imposing group of buildings that make up the Great Lavra, but he had also secured sufficient funding to maintain the monastery and laid the foundations of coenobitic monasticism. In the 11th and 12th centuries, Mount Athos became one of the most important monastic centers in the Byzantine Empire. Many monasteries were founded and the Byzantine emperors issued “chrysobulls” and “sigillia” granting numerous privileges and vast tracts of farmland. At the time when the monastic communities in Asia Minor were being wiped out by Seljuk Turk raids, the monasteries on Mount Athos were flourishing and their landed property was constantly increasing, as was their influence. Mount Athos is a self-governed part of the Greek state, subject to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in its political aspect and to the Ecumenical Patriarch of Constantinople in regards of its religious aspect. The Greek State is represented by the Governor of Mount Athos, who answers to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and who, together with the deputy governor, resides in the capital of Mount Athos, the village of Karyes. He ensures that the Charter is respected, attends the sessions of the Holy Community in an advisory capacity, and presides over local public services (police, customs, etc.). All women without exception are forbidden to enter to Mount Athos. Mount Athos has been divided into twenty self-governed territories. Each territory consists of a cardinal monastery and some other monastic establishments that surround it. All the monasteries are communes (of a convent nature). That means that there is common liturgy, prayer, housing, nourishing and work among the monks. The Abbot of the monastery, being elected by the monks for life, is responsible for the affairs of the monastery.

Date Range: 960 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Athos peninsula

Region tags: Greece, Macedonia, Mount Athos

Mount Athos

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: S. Kadas, Mount Athos: The Monasteries and their Treasures (in Greek), Athens, 1979.
- Source 2: P. Theocharidis, P. Foundas, and S. Stefanou, Mount Athos (in Greek), Athens, 1991.
- Source 3: Thomas M. Provatakis: Mount Athos: A Brief History of Mount Athos and a Description of Its Monuments, Athens 1983

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://mountathos.org/en-US/Home-en.aspx>
- Source 1 Description: Athos Digital Heritage. Digitization project of the Holy Community of Mount Athos
- Source 2 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/454/>
- Source 2 Description: Unesco World Heritage Convention: Mount Athos
- Source 3 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20071015091555/http://mountathos.gr/active.aspx?mode=el%7B00000000-0000-0000-0000-000000000000%7DView>
- Source 3 Description: Former official page for Mount Athos
- Source 1 URL: <https://athoslibrary.blogspot.com/>
- Source 1 Description: Online Library with studies on Mount Athos

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Notes: The sole responsible for excavations on Mount Athos is the Ephorate of Antiquities of Chalcidice and Mount Athos that belongs to the Greek Ministry of Culture.

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1984-2000

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Zygou monastery

Notes: It is an old Athonite monastery that was founded in the early 10th century and was destroyed just before 1198. It is located approximately 2km east of Ouranoupoli, just outside the limits of Mount Athos, in a position known as Fragokastro (just 40m outside the borders of Mount Athos). It seems that it is one of the oldest monastic institutions on the Athonite peninsula. In the excavation site one may see the castle, the towers and mainly the Catholicon of the monastery which is being excavated. The castle consists of five construction phases, all older than 1211. The surface inside the walls is 5,5 acres and the walls had 11 towers –some of which are being restored.

Reference: Ioakeim Papaggelos. Η αγιορειτική μονή του Ζυγού (Φραγκόκαστρο)-The monastery of Zygos (Fragokastro).

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

Notes: The landscape is marked by τηε mount Athos (2,033 m,6,670 ft). In Greek mythology, Athos is the name of one of the giants that challenged the Greek gods during the Gigantomachy, the battle fought between the Giants and the Olympian gods. Athos threw a massive rock at Poseidon which fell in the Aegean Sea and became Mount Athos. According to another version of the story, Poseidon used the mountain to bury the defeated giant.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: There is an extensive network of paths and mule tracks on Mount Athos, developed over many centuries. Until the second half of the 20th century their use was the only practical way of travelling by land. The principal routes were stone paved, built and maintained to a high standard, with impressive stone bridges. Since motor transport introduced on the peninsula, increasing numbers of roads and tracks have been, and continue to be, built. Their construction has cut through or obliterated many of these paths, most of which had fallen into disuse.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

Notes: The twenty monasteries of Mount Athos resemble mediaeval cities, built as they are in precipitous locations, fortified with strong walls, and with one or two entrances and a spacious open area within the walls. In this area, the courtyard, are the main church, the phiale for the blessing of the waters, the refectory, and various chapels. It is surrounded by the monks' cells, the abbot's quarters and other the auxiliary structures (workshops, warehouses etc). Each monastery is a large complex with its own character, consisting of many buildings constructed in different periods and in different architectural styles and under different architectural influences.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: mountain

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The monasteries and other buildings located on the peninsula were built in different periods. The oldest monastery, the Great Lavra, was built in 963 CE while the newer ones were built in the 14th century. In addition, new cells, hermitages and other ancillary buildings that serve the monastic life are constantly being erected.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: In the twenty monasteries that make up the monastic state of Mount Athos, the coenobitic monastic system is followed. However, in the various cells the worship is individual.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–As the result of pillage

–Other [specify]: The area of Mount Athos has suffered many times in the past pirate raids, which resulted in the destruction of monastic buildings. The result of these raids was the adaptation of the architecture to the raids with the addition of fortifications

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Human-caused accident

–Other [specify]: Many cases of fires have been recorded, which destroyed entire wings of monastic buildings.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Notes: Restoration and conservation works, co-funded by the European Union, are performed by the Hellenic State (10th Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities and Centre for the Preservation of the Athonite Heritage). There is on-going collaboration between the responsible services of the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs, Culture and Sports; the General Secretariat of Culture; and other Ministries with the monastic community.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The monastic community of Mount Athos is dedicated to the Virgin Mary.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: In a sense however yes. In the monasteries are kept the relics of the founders of the monasteries, who were recognized as saints by the Church, and in a sense are associated with a spiritual kinship with the monks.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: In 958, the monk Athanasios the Athonite arrived on Mount Athos. In 962 he renovated the big central church of the "Protaton" in Karyes. In the next year, with the support of his friend Emperor Nicephorus Phocas, he built the monastery of Great Lavra, the largest and most prominent of the twenty monasteries existing today. In 972, the Emperor John the First signed the famous "tragos" the first charter of Mount Athos, setting a state of coexistence of eremitic and coenobitic (community) systems.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Other [specify]: monks

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Notes: However, the construction of certain monasteries and/or cells is attributed to miraculous events, or appearances of saints. In fact, many such stories have been recorded linking the founding of a monastery to a miraculous event.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Many monasteries were built, renovated, preserved or painted with the sponsorship of rulers or rich faithful persons-both male and female. Russian tsars and princes from Moldavia, Wallachia and Serbia, until the end of the 15th century, helped the monasteries survive with large donations. Furthermore, many of the cultural and religious treasures kept today at Mount Athos are in fact gifts or were sponsored by such people.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: However, the monasteries at Mount Athos preserve an enormous wealth of historic, artistic and cultural elements, among which manuscripts, incunabula and post-incunabula of the Holy Scripture and of Christian Orthodox sacred texts.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Some monasteries, like the Dionysiou and the Simonos Petras monasteries, are built on the rock, while several small cells have been built on the edge or on cliffs in isolated areas.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s).

Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Square meters: 72

Notes: The monastery of Great Lavra

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Height, meters: 45

Notes: The so-called tower of Milutin.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– Height, meters: 25

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Bricks

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

Notes: Only at the refectory of the Monastery of Dionysiou there are wall paintings on the outside of the building.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Mount Athos has one of the largest densities of wall paintings in the world (100,000 sq.m.). The most numerous and most important examples represent the Macedonian School (13th–14th cent.) and the Cretan School (16th cent.). There is very little from earlier centuries, probably owing to disasters, fires, renovations, and overpainting.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Only Jesus Christ and occasionally the Holy Trinity.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and demons.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are depictions of Saints, monks, Emperors and Princes etc.

- ↳ Are there animals depicted:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - Yes
 - ↳ Floral motifs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: themes with animals/nature
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
 - No
- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

 - Yes
 - ↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
 - No
 - ↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: floral-abstract motifs.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: mosaic with saints

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Reference: . Proceedings of the International Symposium "Inscriptions: Their Contribution to the Byzantine and Post-Byzantine History and History of Art". Wiesbaden:

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: There are wooden sculpted ceilings as well as ornate metal elements.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans
– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives
– Yes

↳ Human narratives
– Yes

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: In every monastery there is a cemetery where the monks are buried. Moreover, there is an ossuary in every monastery where the bones of the monks who died in the monastery are kept, regardless of the date of their death. This means that the monasteries keep the bones of monks who lived centuries ago.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Notes: In some monasteries there are tombs of members of a family of donors or benefactors, however these tombs concern only the male members of the family.

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Those who become monks on Mount Athos are buried exclusively on Mount Athos. This means that the family of every monk can not claim the body after his death.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Through prayer

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: There are many narratives that mention the presence of enlightened/sanctified elders-monks who lived on Mount Athos and perform miraculous interventions on various occasions.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: References to demonic presences are very common on Mount Athos. They are usually presented in the form of a demon who tempts the monks and tries to prevent them from their spiritual life and the struggle to achieve their spiritual goals. Such appearances can take any form, even during work, sleep, dinner/supper, so the temptation arises to keep the monk out of his path of salvation.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: At various instances of the monk's daily life.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Notes: There are many cases where the Athonite tradition has recorded an intervention for the rescue of Mount Athos, either during pirate raids, natural disasters or military operations.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: For the monks it is mandatory. For the visitors is not, however it is strongly recommended.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance is required due to the large number of visitors visiting Mount Athos, and due to the age of the buildings and of the facilities in general

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: That depends. Some monasteries employ permanent staff while other hire the necessary number of skilled workers or craftsmen to perform the maintenance work.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: In 1981, was established by law the Centre for the Preservation of the Athonite Heritage, the exclusive responsibility of which is the execution of projects on Mount Athos, such as restorations, maintenance, construction, infrastructure, energy efficiency projects etc.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: In fact, every visit of each visitor is considered a pilgrimage. Some of them were famous and illustrious, so they have been documented, while pilgrimages-visits, such as that of the Russian monk Vassili Barsky, are important historical sources.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– *specify*: According to the calendar, every monastery, cell or hermitage celebrates the feast of the saint, to which it is dedicated. This celebration is called "festival" and includes ceremonial services, liturgies and other religious events.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– *number*: depending on the number of monks in each monastery-cell and the visitors.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Notes: However, there have been documented prophecies made by some of the elders of Mount Athos and are widely circulated, mostly informally.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Notes: However, the Athonite tradition refers to miraculous healings and similar phenomena.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Large-scale ritual is considered to be the Divine Liturgy that takes place in the "katholikon", the central church of each monastery or the chapel, in the case of smaller monastic settlements.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Smaller-scale rituals are considered to be some services that take place after lunch and dinner, blessings, inauguration of a certain facility etc.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Normally all the monks who live in the monastery and all the lay people who are visitors at any given time.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: daily

Notes: On a daily basis, all kinds of services are held, vigils, etc. Special and large-scale services take place during the feast of the honored saint of the Monastery or during the great feasts of the Orthodox Church.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Every year each of the twenty monasteries elects its representative to the Holy Community (Iera Koinotita) which exercises administrative authority, while the Holy Supervision (Iera Epistasia) exercises executive authority and consists of four members, elected by the five hierarchically preceding monasteries. The head of four is traditionally called Protos (First).

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Only males.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The seat of the clerical and secular administration of the Athonite monastic community is Karyes, a settlement situated almost at the center of the peninsula, it is considered to be the capital "city" of Mount Athos (although its population is about 163 inhabitants).

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: In 1749 was founded the Athonite or Athonias Academy, a Greek Orthodox educational institution that offered high level education. The Athonias was closed in 1821 when the Greek war of Independence broke out and reopened in 1845 in Karyes, the administrative center of Mount Athos. It was financially supported by the monasteries and the monks of the region. In recent years, the Academy provides high school education. The students are interns (food and accommodation are provided free of charge). All the necessary facilities for living are available, such as washing machines, dryers, sports games, board games, books from its modern library, computer room with modern computers, physics-chemistry laboratory, etc. The curriculum includes Church music, hagiography, liturgical studies, Mount Athos History, biblical and patristic exegesis, ethics, etc.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Mount Athos is a self-governed part of the Greek state, subject to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in its political aspect and to the Ecumenical Patriarch of Constantinople in regards of its religious aspect. The Greek State is represented by the Governor of Mount Athos, who answers to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and who, together with the deputy governor, resides in Karyes. He ensures that the Charter is respected, attends the sessions of the Holy Community in an advisory capacity, and presides over local public services (police, customs, etc.).

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: The Greek State is represented by the Governor of Mount Athos, who answers to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and who, together with the deputy governor, resides in Karyes. He ensures that the Charter is respected, attends the sessions of the Holy Community in an advisory capacity, and presides over local public services (police, customs, etc.).

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Notes: Only partially. Additional income comes from the visitors, who pay an entrance fee (a kind of visa), but also from the management of properties, which are located outside Mount Athos.

Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Notes: In 971/72, at the instigation of the Byzantine emperor Ioannis Tzimiskes, Euthymios, the Abbot of the monastery of Studios in Constantinople, composed the first typikon, a charter governing the organization and administration of Mount Athos. This text, known as the Tragos because it was written on a parchment of a goatskin and now housed in the tower next to the building of the Holy Epistatia, formed the basis for the later typika and the subsequent development of all the monasteries on Mount Athos.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: According to the tradition, the Virgin Mary with John the Evangelist, on their way to visit Lazarus in Cyprus encountered a stormy sea that forced them to temporarily seek refuge in the port which is now the Holy Monastery of Iviron. The Virgin Mary, admiring the wild beauty of the place asked God to give her the mountain as a gift.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

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